

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: ABBABULGU****FIRST NAME: TENKIR****PROGRAM CODE: DSDD****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: ONE****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 2%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2010 on Windows 11)

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP)(samples below):

1. Essay Writing (EUCLID 2024, 6-14)
2. Punctuation (EUCLID 2024, 15-23)
3. American Vs. British English (EUCLID 2024, 24-32)
4. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2024, 33-39)
5. EUCLID Style Guide (EUCLID 2024, 40-42)
6. CMS Crib Sheet (EUCLID 2024, 43-57)
7. Latin Abbreviations and Expressions (EUCLID 2024, 58-64)

RESPONSE PAPER FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1) INTRODUCTION

Academic paper writing has been a crucial aspect of any tertiary-level academic endeavor. ACA-401D: International Academic Writing course material presented for period one, revised by Professor Laurent Cleenewerck and Dr. Kabiru Gulma in 2024 has been a great help in introducing the student to the Ph.D. program, which is a heavily paper-writing-based endeavor. At all academic levels, students must develop the highest command of academic writing skills and an understanding of their importance (Defazio et al. 2010, 34-47). The course has refreshed my previous learning while introducing me to new knowledge. The course pack has been highly informative, especially in introducing me to my future academic writing expectations.

The course pack is divided into eight chapters. The first chapter was more of a refreshment of previous knowledge for me, but at the same time, it was a learning process. This chapter deals with techniques for writing good academic essays, from preparation to submitting the paper for evaluation. The second chapter, about punctuation, was a relearning and learning experience for me. It stressed how it is crucial to strictly follow

punctuation in academic work. The third chapter was exciting, dealing mainly with the differences between the two prominent English speakers (American and British English). It was an eye-opener. Variations in punctuation, meaning, vocabulary, and the like are explained in this chapter. It also brought to my attention the need for consistency in using the styles. In the fourth chapter, plagiarism, which is a crucial principle in academic writing, has been explained in detail. It also taught me how to avoid the possible risks of plagiarism due to a lack of proper citations and other technical errors. The fifth chapter introduced me to the expected style of Euclid as a student. The sixth chapter is very informative and introduced me to the Chicago style. I mainly worked with the APA, and this was new territory. The seventh chapter is the most interesting one. The Latin expressions and abbreviations introduced were highly informative. The last chapter has helped show me how the advisors will make future corrections to my papers. In this response paper, I will focus on chapters one through seven. I will use the title of each chapter as a heading to forward my responses.

2) ESSAY WRITING

Essays can be of many types in terms of the nature of categorization. However, in general, they are categorized as academic and non-academic. Scholarly essays follow strict styles and rules. The chapter starts with tips for writing successful academic essays. These are starting as early as possible to get enough time, defining and analyzing the questions, the first drafting, which included jotting down initial thoughts about the topic and putting an essay plan as a guide for the work, researching the topic, note-taking, developing and organizing of the essay plan, drafting, editing it up to turning-in has been very helpful in refreshing my previous learning. The part where the illustration of the introduction, body, and conclusion elements on page 10 has been to the point and very informative (EUCLID 2024, 10).

The section that reminded me of the need for referencing, editing, and re-editing has been a great reminder. "The Rule of Thumb for Writing a Paper" has great suggestions; it helped me organize my knowledge better in essay writing. The tip on the dangers of forwarding sweeping generalizations, especially the part that states, as it is noted, "such remarks add nothing of substance... they suggest that the writer is unsure what to say and is looking for a way to fill some space (EUCLID 2024, 10) is a great tip.

This chapter has been very informative and helpful as a Ph.D. student.

3) PUNCTUATIONS

The general rules provided for using punctuation in academic work were in-depth. I have a lot to learn from this thorough information on punctuation usage. The points on using apostrophes to indicate possession and omitted words have been very detailed and informative. The brackets, bullets, colon and semicolon, comma, dashes and hyphens, ellipsis, and quotation marks have been equally enlightening. I should demonstrate a good

command of punctuation at this level of academic standing, and I have learned a lot from this chapter. For example, the section where it explained the hyphen has been entirely new to me.

4) AMERICAN VS BRITISH ENGLISH

This chapter has been one of the most fascinating chapters of the note for period one of this course pack. This chapter is very informative and exciting as well. I always thought American and British English have minor differences, such as accents, spelling variations, and expressions. However, this chapter taught me valuable lessons in many ways. The part where the difference in usage of SBE and SAE was explained gave me a lesson in terms of the usage of has/have, and it has been a great lesson.

The “Ethnolects” mentioned in this chapter have been a new concept for me. I did not know the existence of independent "Black English" and “Yiddish,” but this is an excellent lesson in this paper section. Other concepts like the jargon, the changing cultural references, regional variations, identity, and stereotyping were equally exciting and informative. The differences in punctuation and dates were also new lessons.

5) PLAGIARISM

While plagiarism can occur intentionally or accidentally, it is unacceptable. Plagiarism has been a topic of discussion in most tertiary-level academic works. Plagiarism kills creativity, among other things; the essence of academic writing is learning, originality, and creativity. Plagiarism defeats these purposes in many ways (Graduate-Coach 2023).

I already understand plagiarism well and its position in scholarly works. The chapter reinforced and refreshed my already existing knowledge base about the subject. Plagiarism is not only unfair to the original contributor but also a crime. The lack of it is a clear demonstration of originality and rigorous work. We can avoid plagiarism through proper citation, paraphrasing in a drastic and meaningful way, and direct quotation and citation.

Even though I had a good base of knowledge regarding plagiarism, the section where it discussed "when not to cite" has been very informative and helpful. I had a gap and always wondered if there were any exceptions to citations. Now, I understand that if it is commonly understood knowledge and information repeated in a relatively large number of works that I do not have to cite, this is quite a relief (EUCLID 2024, 33-39).

Generally, this chapter has reinforced my previous knowledge and made discoveries.

6) EUCLID STYLE GUIDE

Even though this chapter is the shortest of the eight chapters in the course pack, it is full of vital information for a student in the university. Even if there are many commonly accepted academic standards, each university has unique rules for producing academic papers for its students.

A style guide is a way for the authors to document their works. Styles give consistency and clarity to academic work.

“The lack of a single authoritative source on style for written English means there is, and will always be, a certain amount of debate on style elements. The use of punctuation and correct grammar is well-established and clear. However, the style is much more than just the correct usage of punctuation, grammar, and vocabulary (Ibid). I learned that "EUCLID recommends the Chicago Rules (Turabian)." EUCLID's recommendation is a preference, not an obligation upon the student. He can use other styles, such as APA, as long as he can consistently use them. Nevertheless, I am planning to follow the recommendation.

The shortness of the chapter did not prevent it from being very important and informative, as I have learned a lot from the rest of the chapters in the coursework.

7) CMS CRIB SHEET

The Chicago Style of formatting is a widely used writing style by scholars. Even though I have never used it for my prior work, this style is an excellent tool for presenting academic work. The Kate Turabian Manual, however, is a new thing for me. This is the first I have heard of it. As I read the chapter, I understood that the Turabian style is the same as the Chicago Writing Style. The Turabian is a student version, while the Chicago style is the professional style (Sterba 2024)

This chapter is very instructive and helpful. The instructions regarding abbreviations and the usage of acronyms have been very informative. For example, “scholarly abbreviations such as, etc., e.g., may only be used in parenthetical comments injected into your text” (EUCLID 2024,). While capitalization has been refreshing my previous knowledge, compound words require more study because they are new and very detailed concepts for me. The adjective compound, serial compounds, and using hyphens with compound words and prefixes seem complex. Despite this, I am confident I will master it as I study and apply it in my work.

The use of italics, quotation marks, and numbers is explained in the text very clearly. However, the part that deals with quotations is even more detailed. The paragraph explaining when we can change quotations is fascinating and new learning. Now I know I can make changes like double quotations to single and correct the initial capitals, punctuations, and typographic errors; this is very helpful. Instructions, such as headings,

lists, and endnotes, are handy and educational. The bibliographies section on books, journals, newspapers, reports, and references also gave me a deep understanding of the Chicago style. Overall, this chapter is indispensable for my Ph.D. study at the university.

8) LATIN ABBREVIATIONS AND EXPRESSIONS

This paper section has been the course pack's most exciting and enjoyable part. Finding this amount of summarized Latin abbreviations and expressions gave me confidence. As I apply these in my future academic works, they not only give a professional look to my work but also enhance the quality of the work. I will use these in my papers.

These lists help my future work and help me understand other scholarly works as I read them.

Generally, I found this chapter helpful in writing my paper and reading and understanding other academic works. Latin abbreviations and expressions are very effective in writing argumentative phrases without taking too much space and also keep the reader of our work from distraction (Nastachowski, n.d.).

Finally, the final chapter on the sample corrections to the paper gave me an idea of what to expect from my supervisors in the future.

9) CONCLUSION

Each chapter in the course pack gave me a great depth of understanding in terms of writing good scholarly essays. The course material has been instrumental in exposing me to crucial essay writing skills that included the proper utilization of punctuations, citations, avoidance of plagiarism, the recommended writing styles, the use of American vs. British English, and the need for consistency in language and referencing styles.

This course pack made me think about how rigorous is going to be the Ph.D. path, especially the dissertation work. From a student's perspective, writing is a tedious task and even a dreadful effort to put ideas to paper while developing mastery of academic writing styles (Defazio et al. 2010, 34-57). I cannot say right now that I have explored and perfectly understood all the information in the course pack, especially the Chicago and Turabian styles, which need some time and experience. However, this is a great start-up.

The only thing I can comment on about this course pack is that it can be expanded slightly more.

Finally, the usefulness of this course pack is not limited to the course time but will also be actively helpful up to the submission of the dissertation. The invaluable information in this material is worth refereeing from time to time because this is an excellent piece of work.

REFERENCES

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